

Noise Exposure Analysis of the New Hybrid-Electric Aircraft Design within the Airport and Fleet Scenario

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ABSTRACT

Hybrid renewable integration, electrification, hydrogenation and their optimization in aircraft design are necessary challenges nowadays for the transition towards low-carbon air transportation systems. The EU EFACA project is concentrated on few new conceptual designs for the aircraft – hybrid-electric propulsion and liquid hydrogen fueled propulsion aircraft. Current paper considers the noise specific issues of the both designs, but with more emphasize on the hybrid-electric propulsion aircraft noise. It is analyzed at aircraft, airport and fleet levels of assessment necessary for new technology proving. For that the sophisticated aircraft noise calculation tools are used and single event, airport and fleet scenarios are designed. First preliminary results for all the scenarios are shown.

INTRODUCTION

The European aviation industry aims to reach the new targets in alignment with the UNFCCC Paris Agreement, 2015 and European Green Deal, 2020. The approach outlined in Destination 2050 (van der Sman et al, 2021) involves a combination of strategies such as adopting new technologies in aircraft designs – including so called disruptive technologies, optimizing operations, utilizing sustainable aviation fuels (SAF), and implementing economic measures. The EFACA (Environmentally Friendly Aviation for All Classes of Aircraft) project (<https://efaca.eu/>) focuses on six main objectives taking into consideration the: three TRL3 demonstrations relevant to the greening of aviation; preliminary design propeller and jet driven airliners using hydrogen fuel; a road map for achieving the EU environmental objectives for aviation. One of them is a preliminary design of an 80-seats 1000-km range propeller driven regional aircraft with hybrid turbo-electric propulsion combining gas turbine and electric engines. The starting point is the consideration of hydrogen fuel cell technologies to select the optimum architecture for the propulsion system.

The new aircraft should be assessed on fuel/energy consumption, engine greenhouse gas (GHG) and local air quality (LAQ) emission and aircraft noise. All the factors must be compared with current ICAO standard requirements (1) and with the targets of the ACARE vision till 2050 (2) – to show that the current and future targets will be fulfilled.

CURRENT STATE OF THE ART

Sustainability in aviation sector is very complex approach depending on aircraft design, fuel-energy usage, operation and service infrastructure. Today it is realized in Clean Aviation program for EU (<https://clean-aviation.eu/>) in such way becoming one of the main drivers for the next generation of aircraft design and sectorial infrastructure transformation. The design of a completely new aircraft moves from a set of top-level aircraft requirements (TLAR) which can be fixed in relation to new market demands. In the present case, design requirements have been fixed by the existing baseline. Transition from the fossil to decarbonized fueled propulsion is a central point of the transformations inside the sector at the moment. Hydrogen plays a very important role in decarbonization of aviation fuel and energy consumption during the flight. Direct fueling the aircraft engines is also a subject of the EFACA project, it considers the investigations and tests of the liquid hydrogen (LH₂) combustion at TRL3 in future engine designs. Also the conceptual designs of the LH₂ onboard storage and system fueling the engines will be proposed.

A hybrid electric propulsion (HEP) aircraft uses a combination of traditional fuel-powered engines and electric motors to provide the thrust for the flight: electric motors will be used for take-off and landing, while conventional engines in cruise flight. Batteries and/or fuel cells are expected to power the electric motors. Currently, the energy density of batteries does not allow for the complete replacement of gas turbine engines with

electric ones without reducing the flight range of regional aircraft. A lot of other challenges prevent the full electrification of aircraft. The degree of hybridization H_p of the HEP – the ratio between the electric motor power and the total installed power, is now a design parameter for new aircraft. The HEP aircraft are expected to replace the conventional for short range air traffic with TLAR for flight distance till 1000 miles and 50-100 PAX onboard capacity – means to be concurrent to ATR-42 and -72 turboprops. Even the modification of these types by inclusion of the HEP subsystems in design is considered as one of possible way for decarbonizing them as a whole. The reference aircraft for the regional traffic sector is the turboprop ATR72-600.

The new HEP aircraft – baseline design – should be assessed for its expected noise exposure in comparison with reference aircraft at three levels of exposure analysis: single aircraft flight event; relevant airport and fleet (regional or global) scenarios. For the first level the ICAO noise certification conditions and current standard values are subject of investigation and comparison – do the modelled noise levels under the limits of the ICAO current and future standards? And how all of them are compared with the reference aircraft first of all. At second and third levels the contribution of the new designs into the overall aircraft noise exposure – around the airport location and globally or regionally – will it be relative with expectation of the current roadmaps till the 2050 goals and targets.

METHODOLOGY OF THE NEW AIRCRAFT AIRPORT AND FLEET NOISE ASSESSMENT

Single flight event noise modelling

Single flight event noise comparisons are provided for both conditions – in accordance with ICAO Annex 16 requirements and real flight operation. ICAO strictly defines the certification conditions for the three main landing-takeoff (LTO) flight stages to accurately assess noise levels at the control points and show their relevance to current limits. These conditions are usually different from the observed in operation, especially in particular airports of consideration. Any desire to compare the measured noise levels in any airport with appropriated certificated levels for any aircraft needs their recalculation from the observed to certification conditions (1) – noise levels are strictly dependent from the specific flight performances and conditions (3). Real operational flight procedure for the engine thrust and flight speed – two parameters mostly influencing the noise of any aircraft (not considering the design parameters) – may be very different from the certification requirements (4) providing the noise level difference of up to 5 dB at the point of noise control (Fig. 1) Even for the approach flight along the glideslope the difference was identified high enough because the thrust due to certification procedure should be stable during the

flight over the control point when in operation a piloting produces the high engine operation mode on 20-50% of the required thrust for stable flight depending on the aircraft type and flight conditions.

Fig. 1 ATR-72-500/600 flight profiles in comparison to the flight profiles of the aircraft analogues at ANP data base, ver 2.3

High-quality input data for the real flight performances assessment has become possible last years due to introduction of ADS-B technology, and the subsequent appearance of flight tracking websites such as Flightradar24 (<https://www.flightradar24.com/>) and FlightAware (<https://www.flightaware.com/>). All of them provide with position and movement data of single aircraft, enhancing the reconstruction of aircraft performance: certain surveillance data such as position, altitude, velocity, and vertical speed are broadcast and received constantly around the airports worldwide by a number of ground receiver networks (5, 6). Aircraft-specific noise levels around the flight path are interpolated based on the EUROCONTROL Aircraft Noise and Performance (ANP) database (7). To obtain the final noise levels few adjustments via the ADS-B reconstructed aircraft performances are applied to the ICAO Doc 9911 (8) flight path assessment for more accurate noise level calculation.

The horizontal dispersion of realized flight tracks close to runway (instead of their nominal presentation in AIP of the airport) can affect the acoustic situation in the vicinity of the airport, changing the shape of the noise contours, determining the boundaries of the real noise exposure which is necessary for zoning of the residential development inside the area of concern (Fig. 2). The track dispersion is essential for both – arrivals and departures of the aircraft, which usually enlarge the noise contour areas and also deviate the noise levels measured at monitoring terminals around the values defined by stable flight just along and over the nominal tracks defined in AIP (Fig. 3). For example, the average values and deviations for measured noise levels produced by ATR-72-500/600 at terminals of the NMS in Gdansk are shown in Tab. 1. Thus, an important task for better comparison between measured and calculated noise levels is to take into account the actual flight trajectories when modelling noise exposure

(contours) and substantiating the boundaries of residential restriction zones, as well as comparing the sound exposure levels *LAE (SEL)* obtained as a result of modelling and measurements (Tab. 1).

Fig. 2 Flight tracks realized during the departures (a) and arrivals in Gdansk airport by ADS-B reconstruction

Tab. 1 Measured noise level SEL produced by ATR-72-500/600 at NMS terminals in Gdansk airport

Terminal	SEL _{meas}	$\sigma_{SEL_{meas}}$	SEL _{max}	SEL _{min}	ΔSEL_{calc}
MON 1	64,3	3,2	69,6	59,0	0,7
MON 2	79,1	2,4	88,0	74,0	0,5
MON 3	67,9	4,0	76,9	61,9	1,1
MON 4	78,4	2,1	88,1	71,7	0,5

Fig. 3 ATR-72-500/600 noise footprint in comparison the aircraft analogues Dash-8-300 and Domier-328 from ANP data base, ver 2.3 on the map of airport Gdansk (the circles identify noise monitoring terminals locations close to airport)

Second point of the single flight event investigation is a noise footprint assessment usually for exposure sound level of the value close to the certification limit. The noise footprints (for example for the SEL=90 dBA) may show the area dimensions of the noise exposure produced by flight event in such way to be

compared with noise contours used for the noise zoning of the airport and better understanding of their contribution to these contours. Comparisons of the footprints form different aircraft types is also appropriate assessment of their acoustic performances, for example between the reference and baseline aircraft under the consideration.

The third important point of the modelling of the reference and baseline aircraft noise at the certification and/or monitoring point close to the flight path is an assessment of the contribution of any specific acoustic sources for these types and justification the dominant sources among them – to define efficient ways of noise reduction of the aircraft as a whole.

During the certification and environmental noise measurements the influence of the sound propagation issues, especially the reflecting ground surfaces along the sound wave spreading, is big due to the reflection of sound waves which may interfere with direct sound waves at microphone location – it is so-called ground effect. First of all, the ground effect depends on type of ground surface – the acoustically soft (like the grass covering) and hard (like the concrete covering) are the widely usual types to be considered in airport are and its vicinity. Also the angle of sound wave incidence is an important parameter for ground effect assessment. Ground effect is observed at noise control points just under the flight path and at aside points – where it is higher because of the bigger angle of incidence. Because of the influence of microphone location height of the angle of incidence it is important to take in consideration that in AN certification procedures its height is 1.2 m and for usual NMT it is 4 m. This microphone height influence on spectral AN assessment is shown in Fig. 3. The calculated AN spectra during the ATR-72-500/600 arrival is much better fitted with the measured spectra at aside NMT location on distance ~600 m to runway end and 200 aside the track.

Modelled noise spectra in Fig. 4a are compared accurately with measured ones showing the necessary adequacy for further steps of evaluation. Contribution of the main acoustic sources is found the same as in previous studies (9). The dominant sources are the propeller and landing gear – both of them need for noise reduction to reach the overall noise reduction of the future aircraft designs.

To conduct noise simulations for the airport air traffic scenario, any new aircraft needs to be "acoustically assembled" by incorporating unique noise sources related to the novel EFACA aircraft technologies and configurations, using data-driven methods. Both novel noise sources (such as those specific to hybrid electric propulsion, HEP) and common noise sources (like landing gear noise) will be integrated to create a comprehensive aircraft noise model. This will involve using semi-

empirical models and generating ANP data for them. Aircraft noise exposure is calculated using tools that have been verified by ICAO CAEP for their adherence to ICAO Doc 9911, including IsoBella, AEDT etc. (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4 Aircraft ATR-72-500/600 noise spectrum (SPL) modelling at monitoring site: SPLmeas – measured aircraft noise; SPLsum – calculated overall aircraft noise; SPLPro – propeller noise; SPLAF – airframe noise

Fig.5 Research methodology for the noise assessment of the novel aircraft

Airport noise modelling

Comparison with reference airplane in operation must show the found effect for single flight noise event and for airport scenario in terms of current and future aircraft fleet. To enhance the confidence and accuracy of the assessment, the basic air traffic noise scenario will undergo evaluation through the combination of measurements and calculations. At first stage the Clean Aviation Program considers the elaboration of new technologies for the aircraft of Regional Aviation (<https://clean-aviation.eu/>): both new conceptual designs in EFACA project related to RA types.

Grounding on analysis of RA airports in European region, their air traffic and aircraft fleet it was proved that the Gdansk airport is a good example for the airport scenario modelling of all new elaborations in EFACA projects. For the LH₂ aircraft in design it was preliminary proved the Airbus-320neo as a reference aircraft type. Today the 75% of the air traffic in Gdansk airport is provided by flight of the Airbus-320/Boeing-737 group and over 20% by RA aircraft (jets and props) as shown in Fig. 6. Before the COVID pandemic the contribution of the turboprops in air traffic was much higher – till the 15%. The observed and measured data during last decade for both aircraft groups are analyzed for better modelling of the airport scenario in EFACA project - *EFACAport*.

Fig.6 Structure of aircraft fleet in Gdansk air traffic due to EUROSTAT

In Gdansk airport the ICAO Balanced Approach (10) to aircraft noise management is realized in many aspects (11): aircraft fleet is improved continuously by implementing modern and quiet airplanes; noise zoning was established due to ICAO requirements and in accordance with Polish rules for environment protection from noise (Fig. 7); noise monitoring system was installed for measuring the noise exposure and their data are communicated with community via Internet and other media resources.

Fig.7 The boundaries of the restricted landing use in Gdansk airport

Quite specific form of the noise zones in Gdansk airport are defined by priority usage of the Western direction of the runway for the departures/arrivals

due to existing wind rose in airport location. Around the 75% of the flights are realized at azimuth 293.00°GEO. Such air traffic provides the L_{DEN} (day-evening-night level index) contours used for boundaries assessment to be quite similar with noise exposure footprints defined for single flight event produced by the Airbus-320neo and ATR-72-500/600 – Fig. 8 and 9.

Fig. 8 Aircraft ATR-72-500/600 SEL contour (from Fig. 3) in comparison with 55 L_{DEN} contour (from Fig. 7) of Gdansk airport

a)

b)

Fig. 8 Aircraft Airbus-320neo noise SEL footprint contour in comparison with 45 L_{DEN} contour of Gdansk airport

Air traffic in EFACApport flight scenario is produced in accordance with necessary dominance of reference aircraft type – HEP or LH₂ – to define the effect of any proposed technology for their overall noise reduction. In principle the approach is very similar with proposed in (12). For better noise efficiency analysis the substantiation of the two alternative baseline scenarios was analyzed below to assess the impact of EFACA technologies on noise pollution in the airport vicinity:

- **Baseline A Scenario** that should demonstrate assessment of HEP aircraft technology (Technology A);
- **Baseline B Scenario** based on LH₂ aircraft technology (Technology B).

Aircraft fleet noise modelling

By addressing both emissions and noise, EFACA project contributes to the development of aircraft that are not only climate-neutral but also community-friendly, thereby enhancing the overall sustainability of the aviation industry. The sensitivity analysis conducted currently in EFACA project indicates that the contribution of turboprop aircraft to the overall fleet composition should be at least 15%. However, this figure does not align with the average data reported by EUROCONTROL and EUROSTAT for 2023 concerning the current European fleet structure.

Although the new technologies might be evaluated at a vehicle-level at first stage, further their environmental impact should be assessed at a fleet level considering the entire aircraft fleet composition and number of movements, flight procedures, and replacement strategies. For the global/regional noise and emission assessment the models essentially require operations by aircraft type and flight distance. The EFACA commercial aircraft fleet is reduced to four representative-in-class aircraft on the basis of aircraft physical characteristics, and aircraft noise and engine exhaust emissions – they are also selected to be used as baseline cases for the high-level assessment of the environmental benefit of novel aircraft technologies. The four representative-in-class aircraft are able to accurately approximate the distribution of the fleet sound-levels in the specific airport scenarios tested (12). These aircraft categories and the aircraft selected as representative-in-class are consistent with the selection of reference aircraft for aircraft technology studies conducted by the ICAO CAEP. The reduction of the aircraft fleet to a number of generic or representative aircraft types seems to be a valid approximation for computing noise outputs around airports. With this simplification both noise contours and noise contour areas are computed with minimum uncertainty (13).

CONCLUSION

The EU project EFACA has reached the halfway point of its implementation. The principles of the noise exposure assessment are defined and outlined in the paper. Their improvements are expected at further steps of the project due to new findings in project itself and in other projects of the EU Clean Aviation Program.

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